

Department of Psychology

**Vitamin D and Psychosis:
A Systematic Review of Neurobiological Mechanisms and Brain
Networks Involved in Hallucinations and Delusions**

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PSY-2002

Spring 2025

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Word count: 6899

Abstract

This systematic literature review explores whether vitamin D deficiency may be associated with positive symptoms of psychosis through neurobiological mechanisms and disruptions in the brain's functional networks. Five studies were included: two large birth cohort studies, one cross-sectional study, and two randomized controlled trials. Most studies suggest a potential link between low vitamin D status early in life and an increased risk of later psychosis. In contrast, intervention studies in individuals with established psychosis found no clear effect of supplementation on symptoms.

Although some studies indicate an association between low vitamin D levels and increased risk of psychosis, none of the included studies directly examined neurobiological mechanisms such as dopaminergic activity or functional brain networks. However, preclinical findings and theoretical models suggest that vitamin D deficiency may interfere with the development of dopaminergic pathways and the interaction between the salience, default mode, and central executive networks, key systems involved in the emergence of positive symptoms.

The review highlights a knowledge gap in research on the interplay between vitamin D, dopamine, and the brain's network organization in relation to positive psychotic symptoms. Future studies combining biochemical markers with neuroimaging and clinical assessment of symptoms in early risk phases may provide valuable insight into whether vitamin D deficiency constitutes a neurobiological vulnerability factor for psychosis.

Introduction

Psychosis is a severe psychiatric condition characterized by a profound disruption in the perception of reality. The condition is defined by symptoms such as hallucinations and delusions, that is, sensory experiences that occur without external stimuli, combined with fixed beliefs that are incongruent with objective reality (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013, p. 87). These symptoms, commonly referred to in the literature as positive symptoms, may occur individually or in combination. They represent the core features of psychosis and often constitute the most prominent aspect of the disorder (APA, 2013, p. 122; World Health Organization [WHO], 1992, pp. 86-92, 99-123).

Although psychosis is often associated with the schizophrenia spectrum, there is now broad consensus that psychotic symptoms also occur across a range of psychiatric and neurological conditions, including severe mood disorders such as depression and mania, as well as substance-induced psychoses (Arciniegas, 2015, p. 720; WHO, 1992, p. 123). This transdiagnostic presence, together with the dimensional approach to psychosis introduced in the DSM-5 (APA, 2013, pp. 1-3), has highlighted the need to investigate the underlying biological mechanisms across diagnostic categories. Within a biological framework, increasing attention has been directed toward how early risk factors, both genetic and environmental, may influence the development of brain structures and functions associated with the emergence of hallucinations and delusions (Cui et al., 2021, p. 2708; Davis et al., 2016, p. 185).

There is growing evidence that vitamin D plays a role in brain development and functioning, and that neonatal deficiency may be associated with increased risk for neuropsychiatric conditions such as schizophrenia (Horsdal et al., 2025). This micronutrient has been shown to affect key processes such as neurotransmission, network organization, and structural brain development (Eyles, Burne, & McGrath, 2013, p. 47), yet how these effects may relate to the mechanisms underlying psychotic symptoms remains unclear. Several studies, including a meta-analysis by Cui, McGrath, Burne, Eyles, and Parker (2021, p. 2710), have examined associations between vitamin D and psychosis, but vary in the neurobiological aspects they emphasize. Although some studies touch upon these themes, there is still a lack of comprehensive overviews addressing how vitamin D may influence the development of psychosis in light of biological mechanisms highlighted in a cognitive neuroscience perspective. Thus, there appears to be a need to synthesize current knowledge on how such associations may relate to the emergence of clinical expressions of psychosis, particularly within the domain of positive symptoms.

Against this background, the present systematic literature review examines how vitamin D influences neurobiological mechanisms and brain networks involved in psychosis, with particular emphasis on hallucinations and delusions.

Why investigate vitamin D and psychosis?

The pathogenesis of psychosis is complex, and several studies have highlighted how the neurobiological development in psychotic disorders is marked by considerable heterogeneity and complexity (Davis et al., 2016, p. 185; Roy et al., 2021, p. 581). In particular, the interaction between environmental risk factors and genetic predisposition appears to be crucial in determining whether psychotic symptoms emerge and how they manifest in clinical phenotypes. Further indications suggest that such influences, when occurring during specific phases of brain development in individuals with underlying vulnerability, may contribute to the emergence of psychotic symptoms (Davis et al., 2016, p. 191).

A micronutrient and biologically active compound that has garnered increasing scientific interest in etiological models of psychosis is vitamin D, which has been shown to play an important role in brain function. Vitamin D is primarily synthesized through ultraviolet exposure of the skin, is found to a limited extent in certain foods and supplements and is converted in the body into biologically active forms that can cross the blood-brain barrier and exert neurobiological effects in the central nervous system (Cui et al., 2021, p. 2709). Several studies have suggested an association between low levels of vitamin D and increased risk of psychosis, although the underlying mechanisms remain incompletely understood (Belvederi Murri et al., 2013, p. 235).

The hypothesis that vitamin D may be a contributing factor in the development of psychosis originates from epidemiological observations documenting a higher incidence of schizophrenia in populations with limited ability to synthesize vitamin D endogenously (McGrath et al., 2010, pp. 321-322). This includes individuals born during the winter and spring months, as well as dark-skinned immigrants living in the northern hemisphere, groups characterized by reduced sunlight exposure and therefore lower production of vitamin D (Cantor-Graae & Selten, 2005, p. 12; Coury et al., 2023, p. 249; Davies et al., 2003, p. 587; Dealberto, 2010, p. 325). These observations have since been supported by findings indicating an elevated prevalence of psychosis among individuals raised in urban environments, a factor likewise associated with lower vitamin D concentrations (Davis et al., 2016, p. 188; McGrath & Scott, 2011, p. 245; Mortensen et al., 2001, p. 605).

The link between low vitamin D levels early in life and increased risk of developing psychosis has been confirmed in several large registry-based studies using biological material. Two case-control studies from Denmark, in which dried neonatal blood spot samples were analyzed, demonstrated a significantly increased risk of schizophrenia among individuals with neonatal vitamin D deficiency ($IRR = 2.1$; 95% CI : 1.3-3.5 and $IRR = 1.44$; 95% CI : 1.12-1.85) (Eyles et al., 2018, p. 3; McGrath et al., 2010, p. 890). This association was recently confirmed in a large case-cohort study involving more than 88,000 individuals born between 1981 and 2005, which reported a significant inverse relationship between 25(OH)D levels at birth and the risk of schizophrenia ($HR = 0.82$; 95% CI : 0.78-0.86). The study supports the hypothesis that insufficient neonatal vitamin D status may increase vulnerability to neurodevelopmental disorders, including psychosis (Horsdal et al., 2025, p. 417).

From vitamin D to dopamine: A possible mechanism

Having outlined why vitamin D may be relevant in understanding psychosis, attention now turns to possible neurobiological mechanisms that could explain this association, with a particular focus on the dopaminergic system.

Several studies have indicated an association between low vitamin D levels and schizophrenia (Cui et al., 2021, p. 2708). This is further explored in a systematic review and meta-analysis within the same article, in which the authors included 22 studies comparing vitamin D levels in individuals with schizophrenia and healthy controls (Cui et al., 2021, p. 2710). The results showed that individuals with schizophrenia had a significantly higher likelihood of vitamin D deficiency ($OR = 2.49$, 95% CI [1.17, 5.29], $p = .018$). A similar association was found in first-episode psychosis ($OR = 3.78$, 95% CI [2.40, 5.94], $p < .0001$), supporting the hypothesis that low vitamin D levels may represent a relevant risk factor even in the early stages of illness development.

In parallel, research over the past two decades has provided increasing insight into the role of vitamin D in the development of the central nervous system (Cui et al., 2021, p. 2708). This is supported by findings from animal studies, which provide evidence that vitamin D deficiency disrupts brain maturation and structure, contributing to neurochemical and behavioral phenotypes relevant to the psychosis spectrum (Cui et al., 2021, p. 2712). This growing body of knowledge has particularly drawn attention to the dopaminergic system's vulnerability to vitamin D levels during early neurodevelopment. Several preclinical studies have shown that vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy can disrupt the development of the

dopamine system in the fetal brain (Cui et al., 2010, p. 220). For instance, lower levels of an enzyme necessary for dopamine production have been reported, in addition to findings indicating that dopaminergic neurons develop and distribute differently in the brain compared to normal (Cui et al., 2021, p. 2711; Hawes et al., 2015, p. 197; Kesby et al., 2006, p. 595). Such developmental disruptions in the dopamine system may have broader implications and contribute to an expanding understanding of how neurobiological abnormalities can arise due to early-life environmental influences. Changes in dopaminergic ontogeny appear to represent a key mechanism linking various environmental risk factors for psychosis, providing a biological explanation for why early-life vitamin D deficiency may be particularly relevant to the development of symptoms such as hallucinations and delusions (Eyles, Feldon, & Meyer, 2012, p. 8). This is further supported by animal studies showing that early prenatal administration of vitamin D can counteract dopaminergic alterations induced by maternal inflammation, thereby preventing the development of phenotypes related to positive psychotic symptoms (Luan, Hammond, Vuillermot, Meyer, & Eyles, 2018, p. 10).

Brain networks and cognitive function

Although the association between vitamin D and dopaminergic development represents an important mechanism in understanding psychosis, it does not, in itself, provide a sufficient explanation for the emergence of symptoms such as hallucinations and delusions. Preclinical studies have demonstrated that vitamin D also influences the development of neural networks and is associated with structural and functional changes in the brain (Eyles, Burne, & McGrath, 2013, p. 47). This has prompted growing interest in how vitamin D may affect brain network organization and functional connectivity, an approach that has gained increased traction in recent psychosis research.

In this context, studies have documented an association between positive psychotic symptoms and disruptions in the functional interplay between three core brain networks: the salience network (SN), the default mode network (DMN), and the central executive network (CEN) (Friston, 2002, p. 66; Yuan et al., 2022, p. 2). These network disruptions are understood as manifestations of dysfunctional integration, a central and well-established explanatory model in psychopathology that describes a failure of the brain to coordinate activity across neural systems underlying perceptual synthesis, adaptive behavior, and higher cognitive function (Friston, 2002, p. 66; Yuan et al., 2022, p. 2). The evidence base for this model is further strengthened by a meta-analysis by O'Neill, Mechelli, and Bhattacharyya (2019), which identified consistent disturbances in functional connectivity in the DMN, SN,

and CEN among patients with first-episode psychosis. The analysis revealed hypoconnectivity between the SN and both the DMN and CEN, thereby reinforcing the notion that dysfunctional integration in core brain networks represents a central pathophysiological feature of psychosis.

Although vitamin D was not included as a variable in these studies, they provide a theoretical framework for understanding how vitamin D deficiency, through its influence on brain development and the dopaminergic system, could potentially contribute to functional network disruptions associated with the emergence of positive psychotic symptoms.

Methods

Systematic literature searches were conducted in the PubMed database with the aim of identifying empirical studies with original data that examine associations between vitamin D and psychosis. The searches were carried out in accordance with the principles of PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses). The review was not pre-registered in PROSPERO, as this was not a formal requirement within the context of the present thesis.

Three thematic search strings were developed to illuminate different aspects of the research question:

1. General association between vitamin D and psychosis
2. Vitamin D in relation to dopamine, as a potential mechanism in the development of psychosis
3. Vitamin D in connection with neurobiological networks associated with psychosis, including the functional networks described in the theoretical section (SN, DMN, and CEN)

The searches were manually adapted in PubMed, and relevant MeSH terms and free-text keywords were combined using Boolean operators (AND/OR). The results were assessed for inclusion based on thematic relevance and predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria. No restrictions were placed on publication year or participant age to ensure the broadest possible evidence base. The search was limited to articles written in English or Norwegian. The search strings were as follows:

- Search 1: "vitamin D" AND (psychosis OR psychotic OR schizophrenia OR hallucinations OR delusions)
- Search 2: "vitamin D" AND (psychosis OR psychotic OR schizophrenia OR hallucinations OR delusions) AND "dopamine"

- Search 3: "vitamin D" AND (psychosis OR psychotic OR schizophrenia) AND ("salience network" OR "central executive network" OR "default mode network")

Following the merging of search results, duplicate references were checked, but no overlapping records were identified ($n=0$). Titles and abstracts were manually screened, and potentially relevant articles were reviewed in full text based on the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

- a) Studies examining the relationship between vitamin D and psychosis, with particular focus on clinical symptoms or neurobiological mechanisms
- b) Studies using valid and reliable measures of vitamin D
- c) Studies published in English or Norwegian
- d) Studies with empirically and clinically relevant designs, including observational studies, randomized controlled trials, and other clinical or evaluation-based designs addressing the topic

Exclusion criteria:

- a) Systematic reviews, case reports, and preclinical studies (including both in vitro and animal studies)
- b) Studies examining psychosis secondary to somatic conditions
- c) Studies involving populations not relevant to the research question

Although animal studies were excluded from the results section, relevant preclinical studies addressing dopaminergic mechanisms are discussed in the discussion section to illustrate possible neurobiological explanatory models.

The selection process for the included studies is illustrated in Figure 1 and follows the structure of the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram (Page et al., 2021, pp. 1-6).

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram.

Quality assessment and risk of bias

Methodological quality and risk of bias were assessed according to the design of each study. The two randomized controlled trials were evaluated using the Cochrane RoB 2.0 tool (Sterne et al., 2019), and the assessments are presented in Figure 2. Gaughran et al. (2021) was assessed as having a low risk of bias, whereas Krivoy et al. (2017) was assessed as having "some concerns."

The risk of bias in the three observational studies was assessed using the NIH Quality Assessment Tool (National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute [NIH], 2014). McGrath et al. (2004) and McGrath et al. (2010) were rated as having "good" quality, while Tsiglopoulos et al. (2023) was rated as "fair." All assessments are summarized in Table 1.

		Risk of bias domains					Overall
		D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	
Study	Gaughran et al. (2021)	+	+	+	+	+	+
	Krivoy et al. (2017)	+	+	-	+	+	-

Domains:
D1: Bias arising from the randomization process.
D2: Bias due to deviations from intended intervention.
D3: Bias due to missing outcome data.
D4: Bias in measurement of the outcome.
D5: Bias in selection of the reported result.

Judgement
 High
 Some concerns
 Low

Figure 2. Risk of bias of the included randomised controlled trials.

Analysis and synthesis

The feasibility of conducting a meta-analysis was considered. Due to substantial methodological heterogeneity among the studies, this was deemed inappropriate. There was considerable variation in study design, measures of vitamin D status, and the operationalization of psychotic symptoms and neurobiological outcomes. Consequently, a qualitative synthesis of the findings was chosen.

Results

After screening 440 studies, five were deemed relevant for inclusion. These comprised two prospective cohort studies, two randomized controlled trials (RCTs), and one cross-sectional study. The included studies address various aspects of the association between vitamin D and psychosis, including risk factors, clinical symptoms, and selected neurobiological outcomes. The selection process is illustrated in Figure 1. Following title and abstract screening, 427 studies were excluded. Thirteen full-text articles were assessed for eligibility; one was unavailable in full text, and seven were excluded for not meeting the inclusion criteria. Five studies were included in the final analysis.

The combined sample size across studies was 14,551 participants, with individual sample sizes ranging from 37 to 9,114. Several of the included studies had relatively small sample sizes, specifically $n = 37$ in Tsiglopoulos et al. (2023), $n = 47$ in Gaughran et al.

(2021), and $n = 149$ in Krivoy et al. (2017), which may reduce both statistical power and external validity. Nonetheless, these studies were considered methodologically relevant as they investigated key questions related to vitamin D and psychosis during the early stages of the disorder. Participants' ages ranged from young adults ($M = 19.4$ years) to 65 years. The publication years of the studies ranged from 2003 to 2023, and the diagnostic classification of psychosis or schizophrenia was based either on ICD-10 criteria or registry-based hospital diagnoses. All included studies measured vitamin D status using concentrations of circulating 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] or 25(OH)D₃ in serum. Four studies used direct laboratory analyses, while one relied on maternally reported supplementation (Gaughran et al., 2021; Krivoy et al., 2017; McGrath et al., 2004; McGrath et al., 2010; Tsiglopoulos et al., 2023). The main findings from each of the five included studies are presented below.

Presentation of included studies

An Australian cross-sectional study from 2023 (Tsiglopoulos et al.) examined the prevalence of vitamin D deficiency among youth with first-episode psychosis (FEP), as well as potential associations with clinical symptoms and demographic factors. The sample consisted of 37 participants aged 15-24 years, with limited exposure to pharmacological treatment. A total of 24% had vitamin D deficiency (<30 nmol/L), and 30% had insufficiency (30-50 nmol/L). No significant associations were found between vitamin D levels and psychotic symptoms, depression, cognition, or functioning (all $p > .05$). However, vitamin D levels were significantly associated with the season of blood collection ($\chi^2 = 11.73$, $p = .008$), with the highest prevalence of deficiency observed in winter. Although the study lacked a control group, it provides relevant insight into vitamin D status in the early stages of psychosis and highlights the need for greater clinical awareness of this issue.

Another perspective on the relationship between vitamin D and psychosis is explored in a large, population-based case-control study from Denmark (McGrath et al., 2010), which focused on neonatal vitamin D status and the risk of later developing schizophrenia. Based on data from 424 individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia and 424 matched controls ($n = 848$ total), the study identified a U-shaped association between levels of 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ [25(OH)D₃] in the neonatal period and the risk of schizophrenia in adulthood. This means that both low and high levels of vitamin D were associated with increased risk, whereas intermediate levels were associated with the lowest risk. Compared to the reference category (40.5-50.9 nmol/L), neonates in the three lowest quintiles had approximately double the risk ($RR \approx 2.0-2.1$), and the highest quintile was also associated with a significant increase in risk

($RR = 1.71$; 95% CI : 1.04-2.8). The analyses controlled for a range of potential confounding variables, including family history of psychiatric disorders, migration background, birth-related variables, and degree of urbanization at birth. It was estimated that 44% of schizophrenia cases in the sample could be attributed to abnormal vitamin D levels at birth.

This study was the first to directly examine this association and supports the hypothesis that both insufficiency and excess of vitamin D early in development may increase vulnerability to severe psychiatric disorders such as schizophrenia.

The importance of early vitamin D exposure is further elaborated in a Finnish birth cohort study (McGrath et al., 2004), which investigated whether vitamin D supplementation during infancy was associated with a reduced risk of later developing schizophrenia. The data were based on prospectively collected information regarding the frequency and dosage of vitamin D supplementation during the first year of life, obtained from 9,114 participants in the Northern Finland 1966 Birth Cohort. Among boys, both irregular and regular vitamin D supplementation were significantly associated with a lower risk of schizophrenia compared to no supplementation ($RR = 0.08$ and 0.12). Boys who received at least 2,000 IU per day had a 77% lower risk compared to those who received lower doses ($RR = 0.23$; 95% CI : 0.06-0.95). No similar associations were found among girls or with other psychiatric disorders. The results suggest a possible sex-specific protective effect of vitamin D supplementation in infancy and provide empirical support for the hypothesis that early-life nutritional status may influence neurobiological vulnerability in the development of schizophrenia.

A different methodological perspective on the relationship between vitamin D and psychosis is examined in a randomized controlled multicenter trial from the United Kingdom (Gaughran et al., 2021). This study tested whether high-dose vitamin D₃ supplementation could affect clinical symptoms in individuals with first-episode psychosis (FEP). A total of 149 patients aged 18-65 years, all within three years of psychosis onset, were randomized to receive either vitamin D or placebo and followed for six months. The study found no significant difference between the groups on the primary outcome, total PANSS score at six months (mean difference = 3.57; 95% CI : -1.11 to 8.25; $p = .13$), nor any effect on positive symptoms, negative symptoms, or general psychopathology (all $p > .05$). In the subgroup with confirmed vitamin D deficiency at baseline ($n = 106$), no clinically relevant differences were observed between groups. However, the study revealed a high prevalence of vitamin D insufficiency and deficiency (74.6% and 40.9%, respectively), particularly among participants from minority backgrounds, of whom 93.4% had insufficiency. This indicates that this patient population is at significantly increased risk of suboptimal vitamin D status.

Finally, a double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial by Krivoy et al. (2017) examined the effect of weekly vitamin D supplementation (14,000 IU) in patients with chronic schizophrenia and residual symptoms undergoing clozapine treatment. A total of 47 participants with low vitamin D levels and persistent psychotic symptoms (PANSS > 70) were included and followed over eight weeks. The study found no significant differences between the groups in changes in total PANSS scores or subscales for positive, negative, and general symptoms (all $p > .05$). No effects were observed on depressive symptoms or metabolic profile. However, the vitamin D group showed a trend toward improved cognitive function, specifically in attention and memory domains, although the effect was small (*Cohen's d* = 0.17) and no longer statistically significant after correction for multiple comparisons. The study indicates no significant symptomatic effect of vitamin D supplementation in this patient group but suggests a possible cognitive response. Although this finding should be interpreted with caution, it may nevertheless form a basis for further investigation in larger and longer-term studies.

Table 1

Summary of included studies

Author/ year/ location	Design and sample	Vitamin D (range and method)	Outcome measures	Main findings (related to psychosis)	NIH RoB
Observational studies					
Tsiglopoulos et al., 2023, Greece	Cross-sectional; 37 youths with FEP	$M = 47.2$ nmol/L ($SD = 16.4$), range = 14-85 nmol/L; serum 25(OH)D	Positive, negative, cognitive, depressive symptoms; functioning (PANSS, SOFAS)	No significant associations between vitamin D levels and symptom domains. 24% deficient. Significant seasonal variation in deficiency ($p = .008$).	Fair
McGrath et al., 2010, Denmark	Population-based cohort; 2,602 cases and 2,602 matched controls (neonates)	Serum 25(OH)D ₃ ; quintiles: <19.7, 19.7-30.9, 31.0-40.4, 40.5-50.9, >51.0 nmol/L	Schizophrenia diagnosis from registry data	U-shaped relationship: increased risk in lowest 3 and highest quintile vs. reference (40.5-50.9 nmol/L): highest $RR = 2.1$ (95% $CI [1.3, 3.5]$) for lowest quintile.	Good

McGrath et al., 2004, Finland	Cohort; 9,114 males born in 1966	Maternal report of supplementation; ≥ 2000 IU/day vs. lower	Schizophrenia diagnosis from hospital records	77% reduced risk of schizophrenia in those receiving ≥ 2000 IU/day. No effect in females or other disorders.	Good
Randomized controlled trials (RCTs)					
Gaughran et al., 2021, UK	RCT; 149 FEP participants; 6-month follow-up	Baseline: 74.6% < 20 ng/mL, 40.9% < 10 ng/mL; serum 25(OH)D; weekly cholecalciferol vs. placebo	PANSS (total, pos, neg), depression, function, metabolic variables	No significant group differences in symptoms or metabolic measures at 6 months, despite increase in vitamin D levels.	Low
Krivoy et al., 2017, Israel	RCT; 47 adults with schizophrenia on clozapine	Mean baseline: $M = 39.8$ nmol/L; 70% < 50 nmol/L; weekly supplementation vs. placebo	PANSS, MoCA (cognition), metabolic parameters	No effect on PANSS. Trend-level improvement in cognition (MoCA), but not significant after correction.	Some concern

Note. FEP = first-episode psychosis; PANSS = Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale; MoCA = Montreal Cognitive Assessment; SOFAS = Social and Occupational Functioning Assessment Scale; RCT = randomized controlled trial; IU = international units; 25(OH)D = 25-hydroxyvitamin D.

Discussion

Several studies have identified an association between vitamin D deficiency and psychosis, yet the empirical foundation for the underlying biological mechanisms appears limited. This systematic literature review aimed to investigate how vitamin D deficiency may be linked to psychosis, with particular focus on positive symptoms such as hallucinations and delusions. Drawing on both observational and interventional studies, the review sought to illuminate three core aspects of the research question: (1) the general association between vitamin D and psychosis, (2) vitamin D in relation to dopaminergic mechanisms assumed to be involved in psychosis, and (3) vitamin D in connection with functional brain networks associated with psychosis, including the salience network (SN), default mode network (DMN), and central executive network (CEN).

The included studies varied in design and outcome measures, and the total number of relevant publications was limited. This is reflected in a heterogeneous and fragmented body of evidence, which makes it challenging to directly synthesize the findings. None of the

included studies investigated vitamin D status, dopamine-related processes, and functional brain networks associated with psychosis within a single analysis, as these components were defined in the research question and operationalized in the search strategy. Relevant preclinical studies related to dopaminergic mechanisms were excluded from the results section due to methodological criteria, but are discussed below to shed light on possible neurobiological explanatory models.

The association between vitamin D and psychosis

Several of the included studies examine whether vitamin D plays a role in the development of psychosis. The epidemiological studies by McGrath et al. (2004, p. 241; 2010, p. 889) indicate an association between low vitamin D status in the neonatal and postnatal periods and an increased risk of later psychotic disorders. Such findings support the hypothesis that vitamin D deficiency may act as a neurobiological vulnerability factor in the development of psychosis, in line with theories suggesting that schizophrenia and related conditions partly originate from disruptions in early brain development (Murray et al., 2017, pp. 1190-1192). At the same time, findings from McGrath et al. (2010, p. 890) show that both low and high levels of vitamin D at birth may be associated with increased risk, indicating a non-linear relationship. This may suggest the existence of an optimal range for neurobiological development, where both deficiency and excess represent risk factors. The observed risk pattern was limited to one sex, which could imply that vitamin D interacts with biological variables that differ between males and females (McGrath et al., 2004, p. 241). The identification of these associations in two independent, population-based studies increases confidence in their validity. However, it cannot be ruled out that part of the observed association reflects underlying health conditions or environmental factors that influence vitamin D status.

Tsiglopoulos et al. (2023, p. 239) confirmed a high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency early in the course of illness among individuals with first-episode psychosis, but found no significant associations between vitamin D levels and symptom severity. This lack of significant findings may partly be due to low statistical power caused by a small sample size and the absence of a control group. However, it also raises the question of whether vitamin D may primarily serve as a marker of general health or lifestyle factors rather than acting as a directly pathogenic component.

Furthermore, the randomized controlled trials by Gaughran et al. (2021, p. 6) and Krivoy et al. (2017, p. 143) found no significant effects of vitamin D supplementation on

psychotic symptoms, including hallucinations and delusions. In the Gaughran study, the primary outcome was assessed using changes in total PANSS scores, with no observed group differences either overall or on the subscales for positive symptoms. Similarly, Krivoy et al. (2017) found no differences in symptom severity between the intervention and control groups and additionally reported no correlation between changes in vitamin D levels and clinical outcomes. This study included patients with chronic schizophrenia receiving clozapine treatment, which may have influenced the results.

The lack of symptom improvement in these interventional studies may suggest that vitamin D does not exert a direct symptom-reducing effect in established psychosis, or that any neurobiological effects are too subtle to result in clinically measurable changes within the study timeframes. It is also conceivable that vitamin D primarily exerts its effects through developmental processes related to brain structure and function, and that this impact is substantially diminished once neurobiological abnormalities have already manifested. Additionally, it should be noted that both studies employed relatively short intervention periods and included participants with long illness duration and established pharmacological treatment, which may contribute to symptom stability and reduced sensitivity to change. These findings therefore cannot rule out a potential preventive role of vitamin D, an interpretation supported by the longitudinal data from McGrath et al. (2004, p. 241) and the case-control findings from McGrath et al. (2010, p. 889), both of which suggest that adequate vitamin D in early developmental stages may reduce the risk of psychosis later in life.

Vitamin D and the dopaminergic system: Preclinical insights

Although none of the included studies directly investigated dopamine-related processes in humans, there is robust support in preclinical research for the involvement of vitamin D in the development and regulation of the brain's dopaminergic system, of particular relevance to the understanding of psychosis (Kesby et al., 2013, p. 2; Pertile et al., 2022, p. 1; Pertile et al., 2023, p. 779; Schoenrock & Tarantino, 2015, p. 54). This is noteworthy given that dopamine dysregulation is believed to play a central role in the emergence of positive symptoms in schizophrenia (Schoenrock & Tarantino, 2015, p. 54).

According to Schoenrock and Tarantino (2015, pp. 56-57), animal models, primarily based on Sprague-Dawley rats, demonstrate that vitamin D deficiency during pregnancy may lead to lasting and subtle behavioral changes in adulthood. These are attributed to disruptions in brain development, including dysregulation of dopaminergic signaling pathways and key proteins involved in neurotrophic support and gene expression. Although positive symptoms

such as hallucinations and delusions cannot be directly observed in animals (Schoenrock & Tarantino, 2015, p. 53), hyperactivity in response to novel environments is used as a functional equivalent of psychosis-related agitation and disorganized behavior. Studies have shown that rats exposed to prenatal vitamin D deficiency develop such hyperlocomotive behavior, supporting the hypothesis that neurobiological disturbances involving dopamine and stress response systems may be a mechanism that increases vulnerability to psychosis (Schoenrock & Tarantino, 2015, p. 53).

In line with these findings, a recent study investigated the development of dopaminergic neurons in the midbrain, a region relevant for vitamin D signaling, brain development, and the pathophysiology of schizophrenia. The study demonstrated that absence of vitamin D during fetal development led to epigenetic alterations in dopaminergic neurons, including upregulation of microRNAs that inhibit normal neural maturation. These findings support the hypothesis that prenatal vitamin D deficiency may disrupt dopamine system development via epigenetic mechanisms, thereby increasing the risk of psychosis (Pertile et al., 2022, p. 4).

A related hypothesis is that vitamin D deficiency in the prenatal or early postnatal period may impair the development of dopaminergic pathways, thereby contributing to increased vulnerability to dysfunction later in life, particularly during adolescence or early adulthood, when psychosis typically emerges (Woo, 2013, p. 267). The literature search conducted for this thesis identified no clinical studies that directly examined the association between vitamin D levels and dopamine activity in individuals with psychosis. This represents a key gap in the literature, especially in light of the plausible interaction suggested by both preclinical models and biological theory. It is worth noting that the interventional studies by Gaughran et al. (2021) and Krivoy et al. (2017), which reported no significant effects of vitamin D supplementation, also did not include neurobiological outcome measures. If dopamine-related changes develop gradually or only manifest within specific developmental windows, symptom-based assessment tools may be insufficient to detect them. Additionally, both studies had limited statistical power, which may have increased the risk of type II error, failing to detect a true effect on dopaminergic mechanisms. Without neurobiological outcomes, it is difficult to assess whether vitamin D may have had effects on underlying dopaminergic processes that were not captured by clinical symptom scores.

Functional brain networks and theoretical links to vitamin D

Although the systematic search did not identify studies directly linking vitamin D to

functional brain networks in psychosis, this remains an area of increasing theoretical interest. Nerhus et al. (2017, p. 750) report an association between vitamin D deficiency and cognitive dysfunction, although the underlying mechanisms remain poorly understood. This aligns with a broader recognition in psychopathology research that complex symptom profiles, such as those observed in psychosis, are unlikely to be attributed to isolated brain structures and are increasingly understood as manifestations of disrupted functional integration between distributed networks (Menon, 2011, p. 484). Building on these observations, several theoretical and empirical works have proposed that psychosis may largely be understood as a disturbance in the functional organization of brain networks, particularly in the interaction between the default mode network (DMN), the salience network (SN), and the central executive network (CEN) (Buckner, 2022, p. 351; Manoliu et al., 2014, p. 428; Palaniyappan & Liddle, 2012, p. 17). Buckner (2022, p. 351) suggests that psychosis may represent a network-level disorder in which imbalance between the DMN and competing systems in the brain contributes to disorganized thinking.

The salience network has received particular attention in this context, as it is closely associated with mechanisms that govern the assessment of whether stimuli are perceived as relevant or not (Menon & Uddin, 2010, p. 655). Palaniyappan and Liddle (2012, p. 24) argue that positive psychotic symptoms, such as hallucinations and delusions, may reflect a breakdown in the brain's salience attribution systems. The salience network, which includes regions such as the insula and anterior cingulate cortex, is highlighted as particularly relevant due to its high density of dopamine transporters, making it especially sensitive to alterations in dopaminergic signaling. Dopamine is believed to play a central role in how these structures evaluate and prioritize sensory and emotional information (Bromberg-Martin, Matsumoto, & Hikosaka, 2010, p. 815). In the context of dopaminergic dysfunction, otherwise insignificant stimuli may be assigned excessive salience, a process linked to prediction errors and false signals of novelty or importance (Haarsma et al., 2021, p. 5320). This may, in turn, contribute to psychotic interpretations of neutral experiences.

Although this theoretical framework does not directly address vitamin D, it provides an important basis for understanding how neurobiological factors, particularly those affecting the dopaminergic system, may result in changes in brain network dynamics. Based on previously discussed findings showing that vitamin D can influence the development and regulation of the dopaminergic system, it appears plausible that vitamin D deficiency could indirectly contribute to functional network disturbances in psychosis via dopamine-mediated mechanisms. The dopamine-dependent functionality of the salience network thus emerges as

a central link between neurobiological disturbances and the subjective symptoms characteristic of psychosis (Palaniyappan & Liddle, 2012, p. 24).

A related perspective concerns the central executive network (CEN), which is involved in higher cognitive functions such as working memory, cognitive control, and information evaluation (Menon, 2011, p. 484). In a study by Lavigne, Menon, and Woodward (2019, p. 175), reduced CEN activation was observed in individuals with schizophrenia. This was most pronounced in participants experiencing delusions and occurred in situations where they were confronted with information contradicting their established beliefs. The weakened network activity was associated with impaired ability to integrate new or conflicting evidence, which may in turn contribute to the maintenance of delusional thinking. These findings underscore the role of the CEN as a neurobiological substrate for reality monitoring and evaluation of one's own beliefs. While the study did not address vitamin D directly, such results suggest that dopamine-related disruptions, previously discussed in relation to vitamin D deficiency, could also plausibly affect the functioning of this network.

Thus, the relationship between vitamin D and functional brain networks emerges as a hypothetical but theoretically plausible mechanism by which vitamin D deficiency could contribute to the development of psychotic symptoms. Particularly in light of findings indicating that both the salience network and the central executive network may be affected by dopaminergic disturbances, and that vitamin D plays a role in regulating the dopaminergic system, this connection appears relevant for further investigation. This highlights the need for future studies that combine biochemical measurements of vitamin D with neuroimaging and clinical symptom mapping, both in at-risk populations and in individuals diagnosed with psychosis. Such studies could help clarify whether vitamin D deficiency constitutes a biological vulnerability factor in the development of positive symptoms such as hallucinations and delusions.

Clinical implications and future research

Although the included randomized trials did not demonstrate an effect of vitamin D supplementation on psychotic symptoms, this may be due to the interventions being implemented too late in the course of illness, or to symptoms already being stabilized by pharmacological treatment. These findings should therefore not be interpreted as a refutation of a potential association, but rather as an indication of the need for more targeted research.

An important methodological limitation is that, despite the systematic structure of the literature search and the use of MeSH terms and Boolean operators in PubMed, relevant publications may have been missed. The combination of keywords addressing psychosis, vitamin D, brain networks, and dopamine was not found in a single study, regardless of how the terms were combined. This highlights the challenge of identifying studies that examine complex interactions across neurobiological levels. The search strategy did not include manual screening of reference lists in relevant articles, which might have yielded additional results. However, the search was deliberately restricted in order to map what emerges explicitly through structured searches, and because the theoretical framework already incorporated insights from related literature.

The findings suggest that there is limited research directly investigating the interplay between vitamin D, dopamine, and functional brain networks in relation to psychosis. It is therefore recommended that future studies employ longitudinal designs and include populations in at-risk phases or with recent onset of psychosis. Studies that combine biochemical assessments, neuroimaging, and genetic or epigenetic vulnerability may provide new insights into how vitamin D affects brain development and function, particularly in relation to symptoms such as hallucinations and delusions.

Given that vitamin D is an inexpensive and well-tolerated supplement, even a moderate effect could be clinically meaningful. It should therefore be examined whether vitamin D might have a preventive role in vulnerable groups with known risk for psychosis development, and whether early supplementation can help reduce symptom burden or enhance cognitive function. The combination of theoretical plausibility, absence of significant risk, and a substantial knowledge gap suggests that this is an area that should be prioritized in future psychosis research.

Conclusion

This systematic literature review has examined how vitamin D deficiency may be associated with psychosis, with particular focus on neurobiological mechanisms and brain networks involved in the emergence of hallucinations and delusions. Although none of the included studies directly addressed these neurobiological aspects, several findings suggest that low vitamin D status early in life may constitute a risk factor for the development of psychosis. In particular, two large population-based cohort studies indicate that insufficient vitamin D exposure during sensitive developmental periods increases vulnerability to schizophrenia.

At the same time, randomized controlled trials show that vitamin D supplementation in individuals with established psychosis does not have a clear symptom-reducing effect, neither in general clinical populations nor among those with confirmed deficiency. This may indicate that any potential effects of vitamin D are primarily relevant during neurodevelopmentally vulnerable phases, rather than in clinical stages where brain structure and function are already substantially altered. Some findings suggest possible improvements in cognitive functioning, but these results are uncertain and require further investigation.

This review reveals a gap in the literature regarding studies that integrate measurements of vitamin D with neurobiological indicators such as dopamine-related signaling or functional connectivity in brain networks associated with positive psychotic symptoms. As such, there is currently insufficient evidence to establish a definitive link between vitamin D and neurobiological mechanisms in psychosis. Nevertheless, the association appears both theoretically plausible and scientifically relevant, particularly given vitamin D's potential interaction with the dopaminergic system and brain network organization.

Future research would benefit from hypothesis-driven designs and the use of longitudinal methods combining biochemical measurements with neuroimaging and clinical symptom mapping, especially in at-risk populations or individuals experiencing first-episode psychosis. Such studies may provide important insight into whether vitamin D deficiency functions as a neurobiological vulnerability factor in the development of hallucinations and delusions, and whether this may have implications for preventive strategies.

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Appendix 1

NIH quality assessment of included studies

Criteria	McGrath et al. (2004)	McGrath et al. (2010)	Tsiglopoulos et al. (2023)
1. Was the research question or objective in this paper clearly stated?	Yes	Yes	Yes
2. Was the study population clearly specified and defined?	Yes	Yes	Yes
3. Was the participation rate of eligible persons at least 50%?	Yes	Yes	Yes
4. Were all the subjects selected from similar populations with prespecified inclusion/exclusion criteria?	Yes	Yes	Yes
5. Was a sample size justification, power description, or effect estimate provided?	Yes	No	No
6. Were exposures measured prior to outcomes?	Yes	Yes	No
7. Was the timeframe sufficient to expect an association?	Yes	Yes	No
8. Did the study examine different levels of exposure?	Yes	Yes	Yes
9. Were the exposure measures clearly defined, valid, reliable, and consistent?	Yes	Yes	Yes
10. Was exposure assessed more than once?	No	No	No
11. Were the outcome measures	Yes	Yes	Yes

clearly defined, valid, reliable, and consistent?			
12. Were outcome assessors blinded to exposure status?	No	No	No
13. Was loss to follow-up after baseline 20% or less?	Yes	Yes	Yes
14. Were key confounders measured and adjusted statistically?	Yes	Yes	Yes
Overall Quality Rating	Good	Good	Fair

Sjekkliste for Innlevering av Bacheloroppgaven. Sett + for oppfylt, - for ikke oppfylt i kolonne lengst til høyre

Del av oppgaven	Krav	Referanse til seksjon i APA7-manual	Oppfylt(+)/ikke oppfylt(-)
Egenerklæring	Jeg erklærer herved at oppgaven er utført av undertegnede, ikke har vært levert til annen eksamen eller annen institusjon og at jeg har lest og fulgt reglene for plagiat slik de er beskrevet i Forskrift for eksamener ved Uit Norges arktiske universitet.	+	
Forutsetning	Jeg har lest og forstått dokumentet "Retningslinjer for skriving av bacheloroppgaven".	+	
Format	Har all tekst dobbel linjeavstand?	2.21	
	Er marger 2.54 cm?	2.22	
Tittelside og sammendrag	Er tittelside, sammendrag, referanseliste, appendiks, tabeller og figurer på separate sider med bare en figur/tabell per side?	2.17	
	Er alle sider nummerert i rekkefølge, med tittelsiden som side 1?	2.18	
	Har tittelsiden tittel, toppteksttittel, kandidatnummer (i stedet for forfatternavn), institusjonsinformasjon? Er sammendraget på 250 ord eller mindre?	2.3 2.9	
Avsnitt og overskrifter	Starter alle avsnitt med innrykk?	2.24	
	Er hvert avsnitt lenger enn en enkelt setning, men kortere enn en hel side? Har alle overskrifter på sammen nivå samme format?	- 2.27	
Forkortelser	Er alle unødvendige forkortelser forkastet og er de nødvendige forklart?	6.24-6.31	
	Er forkortelser i tabeller og figurer forklart i tabell/figuratekst?	6.24-6.31	
Matematikk og statistikk	Er alle matematiske symboler, bortsett fra de åpenbare, og alle greske bokstaver forklart i oppgaven?	6.44	
	Er alle ikke-greske bokstaver som blir brukt som statistiske symboler for variabler i kursiv?	6.44	

	Er alle metriske enheter med numeriske verdier forkortet?	6.27
Referanser	Er alle referanser sitert både i teksten og i referanselisten?	8.4
	Er det sammenfall mellom referanse i tekst og referanseliste med hensyn til dato og skrivemåte?	8.4
	Er tidsskrifttittel i referanselisten skrevet ut (ikke forkortet) eventuelt forkortet slik det er på selve kilden?	9.25
	Er referansene både i tekst og i referanseliste ordnet alfabetisk etter forfatters etternavn?	9.43-9.49
	Er sidetall angitt for alle artikler og bokkapitler?	9.25, 9.28
Tabeller og figurer	Har enhver kolonne, medregnet underkolonne, en overskrift?	7.9, 7.12
	Er tabellen fri for vertikale linjer?	7.17
	Er alle figurer og tabeller henvist til i tekst og nummerert i den rekkefølge de nevnes?	7.5

Note. - = Seksjon ikke angitt i APA-manualen. Basert på APA-manualens sjekkliste for innsending av manuskript: American Psychological Association. (2020). *Publication manual of the American Psychological Association* (7th ed.). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.

Erklæring om bruk av KI-baserte hjelpemidler

Har du i arbeidet med forskningsrapporten benyttet deg av KI-baserte hjelpemidler?

Ja.

Hvis du svarte 'Ja' eller 'Vet ikke' på forrige spørsmål, hvilke hjelpemidler har du brukt? (Du behøver ikke rapportere om tradisjonelle tekstbehandlings- eller referansehåndteringsverktøy som Word, LibreOffice Writer, EndNote eller Zotero.)

ChatGPT 4o.

Beskriv hvordan du har brukt verktøyene du har oppgitt i forrige spørsmål. Vær konkret og grundig.

Verktøyet ble benyttet som støtte i arbeidet med å identifisere relevante fagfellevurderte artikler gjennom søk i databasen PubMed. Det ble brukt til å strukturere søkestrenger og kombinere relevante fritekstord på en målrettet måte. Videre ble det brukt til å oversette sentrale fagbegreper til akademisk presist norsk og engelsk underveis i arbeidet.

Jeg vet at det ikke er tillatt å helt eller delvis generere besvarelser ved hjelp av KI-baserte hjelpemidler og levere dem som om det var mitt eget arbeid. Jeg har redegjort så godt jeg kan for min bruk av KI-baserte hjelpemidler i denne erklæringen.

Ja.